

PRINCIPLES OF MEETING AND TREATMENT OF DORSOPATHIES IN PATIENTS OF DIFFERENT AGES

Odiljanov Ozodbek Odiljonovich

Student of Termiz University of Economics and Service, Faculty of Medicine,
Group 23-16

odiljonnorkulov0@gmail.com

Relevance : Our study provides information about the causes of dorsopathies at different ages, types, criteria for diagnosing dorsopathies, differential diagnosis, treatment and prevention principles. Today, dorsopathies appear in different forms at different ages, and people suffer from their pain syndromes. During life, dorsalgia occurs in 70-90% of the population in developed countries and is observed in 20-25% of people every year. Although an episode of low back pain is often short-lived, about 25 percent of patients later develop chronic pain that causes long-term disability.

Purpose of research: to determine the frequency of occurrence of dorsopathy at different ages and the advantages of the principles of treatment through combined methods

Material and examination methods: The study was conducted in the Termez city medical association of Surkhandarya region. As research material, 60 patients of different ages and genders who suffered from various forms of dorsopathy and were undergoing inpatient and outpatient treatment were taken. From the point of view of gender, 15 of the 60 patients were male and 45 were female. When we calculated in percentage, 75% of the patients taken for the study were women and 25% were men. The interesting part of our study was that both the youngest and the oldest of the patients taken for the study were women. Based on this, it can be concluded that women suffer from dorsopathies more often than men. According to many scientists, the reason why women are more affected by dorsopathies than men is the presence of female hormone estrogens. All patients underwent neurological examinations, examinations by various specialists (therapist, gynecologist, urologist) and diagnostic examinations, including: X-ray, CT, MRI. The conducted investigations were carried out to determine the mode of treatment effect intensity and to select appropriate and effective schemes for inpatient and outpatient treatment, methods of assessment of degenerative-dystrophic spine diseases and selection of treatment plan and to determine contraindications. All outpatient and inpatient patients complained of pain in different parts of the spine. 10 (16.66%) people had pain in the neck area,

30 (50%) people had pain in the back area, 3 (5%) people had pain in the thoracic vertebrae, neck and 10 (16.66%) patients with back pain, 7 (11.66%) patients with all areas of the spine

Conclusion: According to the results of our research, diseases of the spine occur at different ages, the reason for this is given above, and these degenerative dystrophic changes are more common in the cervical and lumbar areas of the spine compared to other areas.